

Gyrochronology of wide binaries in the Kepler field

Kenneth Janes

Astronomy Department, Boston University

Abstract

The rotational evolution of solar-type stars is moderately well-understood up to the age of the Sun. One way to extend the gyrochronology relation to stars of later spectral type is by matching the near solar-type member of each pair of a visual binary star with its later-type companion. The precise parallaxes and proper motions in Gaia Data-Release 2 has made it possible to identify a substantial number of wide binary (common proper motion) stars in the Kepler Mission field of view, many of which already have measured rotation periods. I have identified 313 wide binary pairs in the Kepler catalog. A period-color diagram of 116 of those pairs for which rotations of both components have been measured show that many, but not all of the systems having components of nearly equal color also have roughly equal periods. However, the period-color relation for binary pairs with larger color differences is somewhat more chaotic. In particular, the cooler component of some systems rotates more slowly than the hotter component contrary to the expected trend.

1 Introduction

Although the age-rotation-period relation for solar-type stars is moderately well-understood, for the coolest stars the relation is still quite uncertain. Star clusters provide one approach to find the rotation-period-color relation at a fixed age for stars of F, G and early K spectral types, (see, e.g., Meibom *et al.*, 2015), but the fainter late-type main sequence stars are largely inaccessible to rotational measurements. Another approach to link the period of a solar-type star with that of a later spectral type is to compare the periods of a visual binary system. While the actual age of the pair may be unknown, the two components can at least be assumed to be coeval. Earlier efforts along these lines have been limited by the small number of systems with rotation periods (see Mamajek & Hillenbrand, 2008), but with the Kepler mission Borucki *et al.* (2011), many more periods are now available. There have been at least two studies to search for wide binary systems (common proper motion or CPM pairs) in the Kepler field, Janes (2017) (Paper I) and Godoy-Rivera & Chanamé (2018). For a more complete discussion of the usefulness and limitations of CPM stars for gyrochronology, see Paper I.

Both paper I and Godoy-Rivera & Chanamé (2018) made use of published proper motion catalogs, but because of the lack of precise distance information, there is some uncertainty in the identification of genuine physically-associated systems. Now, with the release of the Gaia Data Release 2 (hereafter DR2) by the Gaia Collaboration *et al.* (2018), high-precision parallaxes are available for all stars in the Kepler catalog. At the typical distances of dwarf stars in the Kepler catalog (a few hundred parsecs or less), the DR2 parallaxes and proper motions allow the separation of wide visual binary components from surrounding field stars with considerable confidence.

2 Wide binary systems in the Kepler field

The recent DR2 of the Gaia mission has dramatically improved the prospects for finding wide binary systems. The highly precise DR2 proper motions and parallaxes make it possible to determine unambiguously whether the two stars are physically close to one another and moving together. I downloaded the DR2 data for stars brighter than magnitude 18.5 in an 8-degree radius field centered at 19h 22m 40s, +44d 30' 00", approximately at the middle of the Kepler field of view, containing information for a little over 3 million stars. I then cross-referenced these with the Kepler input catalog (KIC) to create a catalog of 235611 KIC stars with parallax and proper motion data from DR2. There are several cases of multiple matches in the Gaia catalog with stars in the KIC and a few other cases, with no matches between a KIC star and stars in DR2. I dealt with the multiple matches individually later in the process.

The classic problem of identifying the likelihood that two stars, appearing close together on the sky, form a physical pair was first articulated by William Herschel. But with Gaia, it is possible to go much further, to include the parallaxes and proper motions. The parallaxes of the two stars should be the same, within the errors, and the proper motion differences should be small, although not necessarily zero, because of orbital motion.

Because the Gaia parallax errors for stars in this magnitude range in the Kepler field are so small (typically about 0.025 mas), angular measures can be converted reliably into linear units of AU and AU yr^{-1} . The expected proper motion errors are similar, but in many cases the actual proper motion differences for pairs with the same parallaxes are much larger. If two stars really are physically connected, they will of course be in orbit around one another. So while the proper motion differ-

ences will be small, because of orbital motion, they will not be zero in general. In particular, relatively nearby pairs in small orbits can show substantial proper motion differences, easily detectable, given the precise Gaia measurements. Unrelated stars at the same distance would be unlikely to be moving with such small relative proper motions.

In the context of the Gaia dataset, a “Common Proper Motion” pair of stars consists of two stars, close to one another as projected onto the celestial sphere, with the same parallax within the errors and with the same, or nearly the same, proper motion. Figure 1a shows parallax differences between target stars and their close potential companions, vs the proper motion difference between the two. The range of the figure is set to ± 0.5 mas in parallax difference and $0 - 5$ mas yr $^{-1}$ in proper motion differences. That is to say, the figure is a display of a small part of the total space of parallax/proper-motion differences between close pairs of stars in the catalog. Most of the pairs with larger proper motion differences are unrelated to one another. Figure 1b shows the same for stars in two control samples, where 1200 arcseconds has first been added in turn to the declination of each catalog star and then subtracted. So in the control sample, the target stars are paired with stars that are unlikely to be physical pairs (although, in fact, there are three very nearby, wide pairs that appear in the actual search field as well as in both control samples, but with different angular separations.) The parallax differences between potential pairs in both the real sample and the control sample would be expected to be zero within the errors. As the two figures show, in the real sample (Figure 1a) there are a number of pairs with nearly zero parallax and proper motion difference, but the control sample of Figure 1b does not include any pairs with nearly zero proper motion differences.

The diagram is sparsely populated by pairs, except for the narrow range around zero parallax difference, but with a more extended range in proper motion differences is what would be expected for the motion of stars in bound orbits around each other. Consider, for example, a hypothetical CPM pair with a parallax of 5 mas (200 pc), a separation of 7.5 arcsec (1500 AU), and a system mass of 1.5 solar masses (i.e., a couple of early K stars). Assuming a circular orbit the orbital period would be 4.74×10^4 years and an orbital speed of 0.2 AU yr $^{-1}$, or 1.0 mas yr $^{-1}$. So these are genuine physical systems in bound orbits.

I proceeded with a two-step process to identify likely wide binary systems. After sorting the catalog in order of increasing right ascension, I took each catalog star in turn with a parallax greater than 1 mas (1000 parsecs distance), as the “target,” and I searched in the eastward direction for possible companions that have: 1) An angular separation greater than 7.5 arcseconds; 2) A *linear* separation less than 50,000 AU; and 3) A parallax difference less than 3 times the combined parallax error and the combined parallax error less than ± 0.2 mas; 4) Small tangential velocity differences, allowing for likely orbital motion.

These criteria can be justified as follows: 1) Stars with angular separations less than about 7.5 arcseconds may not have been fully resolved by the Kepler Tele-

Figure 1: Parallax differences vs proper motion differences between pairs of stars in the Kepler field. The figure is limited to a small range of differences near zero; the distribution of pairs centered on zero parallax differences and a somewhat larger range in values of proper motion differences is the expected distribution for bound, physical systems. a) Differences for pairs of stars in the actual sample. b) The same, for two control samples, offset in declination by 1200 arcsec North and South. c) The same as a), but for probable binary pairs only.

scope. 2) The limit of 50,000 AU separation is an arbitrary amount, but while stars further apart might still be bound, the possibility of confusion with random field stars is greater. 3) Stars with larger parallax differences or larger errors are more likely to be field stars. 4) Two stars of total mass, M in solar masses, in a circular orbit around one another in the plane of the sky at a separation S in arcsec will have a relative annual proper motion,

$$\Delta_{pm} = 2\pi \frac{M^{1/2}}{S} P^{3/2},$$

where P is the average parallax of the two stars. In general, the proper motion difference will be smaller than this number, but it could also be substantially larger. I selected a cutoff of ten times Δ_{pm} to be certain of sweeping up systems far from apastron in elliptical orbits.

The initial selection process yielded 601 possible pairs. The second step is to calculate their probability of being physically associated. The likelihood, \mathcal{L}_f , that given a target star at some location in the five-dimensional space of RA, Dec, parallax, RA proper motion and Dec proper motion, a possible companion star, separated from the target by the angular distance, S , is an *unrelated* field star, is approximately:

$$\mathcal{L}_f = N_f \times D\pi S^2 \Delta P \Delta pm_{RA} \Delta pm_{Dec},$$

where N_f is the number of stars in the search field and $D(b, p, pm_{RA}, pm_{Dec})$ is the density distribution of stars at galactic latitude, b , as a function of parallax, p , proper motion in right ascension, pm_{RA} , and proper motion in declination.

This likelihood can be further approximated by taking the product of the following marginal distributions of

components of D :

1. The average number of potential companions per unit solid angle at the galactic latitude of the target times the area of the (semicircular) area within S , $\mathcal{L}(S, b)$;
2. The fraction of stars in the search sample per milliarcsec at the target parallax as a function of the parallax difference and the parallax error, $\mathcal{L}(p, \sigma_p)$;
3. The likelihood that a candidate pair with proper motion difference, Δ_{pm} and error $\sigma_{\Delta_{pm}}$ will be drawn from the sample, $\mathcal{L}(pm, \sigma_{pm})$.

The product of these three factors gives the probability that in a single trial a target will be matched with a companion with the desired properties. So to find the probability that in the complete sample, it would be possible to find an unrelated companion to match to the target star:

$$\mathcal{L}_{CPM} = N_f \times \mathcal{L}(S, b) \times \mathcal{L}(p, \sigma_p) \times \mathcal{L}(pm, \sigma_{pm})$$

The MAST archive includes photometry for the Kepler stars compiled from a variety of sources, including in particular, the g-K photometric index for nearly all stars in the catalog and B-V photometry for many of them. In Paper I, I developed a simple relation to transform g-K to B-V so that only three stars in the wide binaries list (KIC 8631751, KIC 10068797 and KIC 12254819) do not have B-V photometry. For these, I searched The SIMBAD astronomical database ((Wenger *et al.*, 2000)).

To make the final list of wide binaries suitable for probing stellar rotations, I removed several pairs that have a close companion (within 7.5 arcsecs) to one of the two components. Several of these may be genuine triple systems, but in any case the presence of the companion complicates the primary purpose of this study.

3 Rotation Periods

For the rotation periods, I combined the results of Paper I and McQuillan *et al.* (2014) (hereafter MCQ). Both the Paper I and MCQ periods were derived from the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the Kepler photometric series, and as I showed in Paper I, the results were nearly identical, except for a few stars where there was a two-to-one period difference; here, I used the Paper I period. Such period-aliasing is in fact a problem for finding periodicities from regular photometric sampling.

I also searched for periods from García *et al.* (2014), Reinhold *et al.* (2013), Nielsen *et al.* (2013) and Metcalfe *et al.* (2014). Most of the stars in these other studies were also measured by MCQ, but I was able to add two stars with periods in the Reinhold *et al.* (2013) list (KIC 4242147, and KIC 6063220)

In these other studies, various methods were used to find rotation periods. For the most part, their results are in good agreement with Paper I and MCQ, but several of the Reinhold *et al.* (2013) periods were one-half the values of the other studies, and there were several other stars with large period differences compared to the Paper I or MCQ values.

As MCQ and others have shown, rotation periods can be extracted from the Kepler data for about half of the late-type stars; I was able to find periods for both com-

Figure 2: Rotation periods vs B-V color index for CPM stars in the Kepler field. The blue dots represent the hotter star of each pair and the red dot is the cooler star. The orange circle represents the location of the Sun.

ponents for 116 systems.

4 Gyrochronology

Figure 2 shows the period-color diagram for the 116 systems that have published periods for both components. In the diagram, the hotter star of a pair is indicated with a blue dot and the cooler star with a red dot; the lines connect the two stars of each pair. The position of the Sun is shown with an orange symbol. Although this diagram is consistent, in a general way, with the gyrochronology concept in the sense that there is a more or less regular relationship between the periods of the two components, in detail the picture is somewhat chaotic. In particular, there are a number of outliers that are not at all consistent with a simple gyrochronology model (see, e.g., Barnes, 2010; Barnes *et al.*, 2016) where at fixed age, the period increases with increasing B-V color index (i.e., with decreasing mass or later spectral type). Furthermore in several of the systems in this figure one or both of the components have periods of only a few days. Some of these can likely be explained as hierarchical triples consisting of a rapidly-rotating, tidally-locked pair and a distant companion, and the small number of systems consisting of two rapidly-rotating stars may be young star systems still in the “C” phase of evolution as described by Barnes (2010). The other discordant systems in this figure are more difficult to explain.

There is a wide range in the photometric amplitude of the rotational modulations of active stars. Both Paper I and MCQ included measures of the photometric amplitudes for the active stars. Figure 3 is a plot of the amplitude the blue component of each pair against the amplitude of the red component, using data from MCQ and Paper I, scaled to the Paper I values. Although there is a suggestion of a correlation between the blue-star and red-star amplitudes, there also is a large dispersion in the relative activity levels of the blue stars vs the red stars.

As solar-type stars spin down with age, there is a corresponding decrease in their activity level (see, e.g. Barnes, 2010). So a separation of stars by activity level might be expected to separate mostly younger stars from mostly

Figure 3: The log of the photometric amplitudes (V) of the rotational modulation of the blue components of each pair vs the same for the red component. Data from paper I combined with MCQ data rescaled to the Paper I values.

older ones. But it is also more difficult to measure the periods of the less active stars. For the purpose of exploring the rotational evolution of late-type stars, I extracted two groups from the list, those where the photometric amplitude of both stars of a pair is $V > 250$ on the Paper I scale and those where the photometric amplitude of both stars is $V < 250$. There are 67 pairs in the former list and 21 in the latter, leaving 28 pairs with a mixture of activity levels. The more active pairs are shown in Figure 4 and the less active pairs are in Figure 5. The two curves in these figures are theoretical isochrones kindly provided by S. Barnes (see also Barnes, 2010) for 1 Gyr stars (dot-dashed green curves) and for 3 Gyr stars (dashed purple curves). The theoretical curves converge to zero period near $B-V = 0.45$. There is a definite concentration of shorter periods in the active star group, and a bias toward longer periods among the less active stars, but in both groups there is considerable scatter.

If the angular momentum evolution of a star is a simple function of its mass once the star has reached about 600 million years of age, as discussed by Barnes (2010) and others, then binary stars with components of almost equal color should have correspondingly nearly equal periods; for systems with a larger color difference, the redder component should have a longer period than the bluer one as the isochrone tracks in Figures 4 and 5 show. Figure 6 shows the blue star periods vs the red star periods for all pairs in the sample. Except for a sprinkle of systems with very short red-star periods and much longer blue-star periods, there is a clear lower envelope near the one-to-one line.

Figure 7 shows the same just for pairs which have the same $B-V$ color index within 0.2 mag. In this figure,

Figure 4: The period-color relations as in Figure 2 for systems where both stars show large amplitudes. The lines show theoretical period-color isochrones kindly provided by S. Barnes (see also Barnes, 2010) for stars of age 1 Gyr (dot-dashed green curve) and 3 Gyr (dashed purple curve).

Figure 5: The same as Figure 4 for systems with small amplitudes.

Figure 6: Periods for the blue components vs the same for the red components. The straight line has a slope of one

there is a concentration of stars close to the fiducial line, but also a considerable population of stars well above the line.

5 Summary

The publication of the Gaia DR-2 catalog has made it possible to identify a substantial number of wide binary systems which can be used to relate the rotation periods of coeval stars of different spectral types to one another. While there is a general trend that longer-period F, G, and K stars are paired with correspondingly long period K and M stars, a considerable number of systems follow an apparently anomalous period-color relation.

There are several possible explanations for this behavior.

The distribution of parallax and proper motion differences in Figure 1 suggests that a small number of the pairs could be in fact, physically unrelated stars. That could explain a few of the apparently wildly deviant systems that are particularly evident in Figure 2.

Since the measurement of the rotation periods depends on the passage of (an unknown number of) starspots across the stellar surfaces, both 1:2 and 2:1 period aliases are entirely possible. It would be possible to hypothesize 2:1 adjustments to the periods of several stars in Figures 4 and 5 to make a much better match of those particular pairs to the isochrones. However, additional photometric or spectroscopic measurements would be necessary to justify any individual cases.

The most likely explanation for the most rapidly-rotating (less than about 5 day periods) late-type stars in Figure 2 is that they are tidally-locked to close companions. Among wider pairs, it is also possible that more subtle interactions could alter their period evolution and

Figure 7: Periods for the blue components vs the same for the red components for systems with B-V color index differences less than 0.2. The straight line has a slope of one

might explain some of the less dramatic anomalies in the period-color relation.

Finally, a possible explanation for the apparent period anomalies is that there is a non-uniform rate of evolution in the rotation periods of the late-type lower-mass stars. There is, in fact, something of a pile up of the cooler stars with periods in the 15 to 20 day range. Newton *et al.* (2016) and others have commented on gaps and other irregularities in the distribution of rotations in the cooler stars.

So while the rotational properties of these wide binary systems reaffirm the general idea of a progressive rotational evolution of the late-type stars, there appears to be several complicating factors that limit with the determination of the rotational age of an individual star.

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